

The Tapestry of Ambivalence: Love and Hate in User Responses to AI Recommendations

[Yue Wu]

Stockholm Business School
Master's Degree Thesis 30 HE credits
Subject: Advertising and PR
Program: Marketing Communication, 120 HE credits
Spring semester 2025
Supervisor: [Jonathan David Schöps]

Stockholm Business School

Abstract.....	3
1. Introduction.....	4
2. Literature review.....	6
2.1 Recommendation Systems as Agents of Platform Power.....	6
Platforms and recommendation systems.....	6
Algorithms as non-neutral agents shaping attention, desire and choice.....	7
From personalization to manipulation.....	8
2.2 User Emotions and Review Cultures in Platform Environments.....	9
Expression on social media and community dynamics.....	9
Social media as sentiment expression portal.....	10
2.3 Ethical Debates and Algorithmic Governance.....	10
Ethical debates constitute a central focus for users in articulating their emotional responses.....	10
Tensions between community ethics and platform monetization.....	11
The power of the filter bubble and users’ resistance.....	12
3. Theoretical framework.....	12
3.1 ANT in Digital Research: Reassembling the Social.....	12
3.2 Latour’s Theories and Its Significance to This Research.....	13
4. Methodology.....	16
4.1 Netnography.....	16
4.2 Following Actors, Tracing Mediators and Analyzing Controversies.....	17
4.3 Platform Selection and Data Collection.....	18
5. Findings.....	20
5.1 When Algorithms Function as Non-human Mediators.....	20
5.2 The Network Constructed Around AI Recommendations.....	21
5.3 Network ‘Turbulence’.....	24
5.4 User Resistance as Network Negotiation.....	25
5.5 Platforms as Affective Infrastructures.....	27
5.6 Network Participants Endeavor to Unravel the “Black Box”.....	29
6. Discussion.....	30
6.1 Theoretical Implications.....	30
6.2 Practical Implications.....	32
6.3 Limitations and Future Research.....	34
7. Conclusion.....	35
References.....	37

Abstract

This thesis examines the increasingly heated discussions surrounding intelligent recommendation systems on social media, investigating how users' mentalities and emotional reactions to AI-generated recommendations foster the evolution of review culture and the development of online communities. Leveraging Actor-Network Theory (ANT) and netnography methods, this study explores the complex relationships among users, algorithms, and digital platforms in social media environments, such as Reddit and Facebook. Through qualitative analysis of 170 user-generated posts and comments, this research investigates users' ambivalent emotions, their skeptical attitude towards algorithms, the emergence of user autonomy, and the community norms formed around AI interactions. The findings show that, as a non-human mediator, the AI intelligent recommendation system has actively facilitated a network involving multiple stakeholders. However, such a network does not seem stable at present. Users are attempting to break the obvious power relations through emotional expression and interaction within online communities. The study contributes to platform studies, digital sociology, and consumer research by regarding user-generated content as a concentrated force of resistance in the current context and incorporating intelligent recommendation systems into the latest discussions on human-machine relationships. Practical implications are offered for platform designers, developers and policymakers, to support more transparent and community-oriented intelligent recommendation systems.

Keywords:

AI recommendation systems; user emotions; review culture; Actor-Network Theory (ANT); netnography; social media platforms

1. Introduction

The “digitized” lifestyle of modern individuals is increasingly becoming a necessity rather than a choice, as people find themselves situated within an environment dominated by digital platforms. The rapid expansion of global e-commerce and the advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) technology have led to web users receiving machine-generated product or service recommendations across diverse digital environments, including e-commerce platforms and social networks, on a daily basis. Talled by Statista (2023), as of January 2023, there were approximately 5 billion social media users globally, representing about 59% of the world’s population. Over half of the global population is being greatly influenced by AI-generated content recommendations, leading to notable changes in their lifestyles (Bojic, 2024). The growing dominance of digital platforms in everyday life has made algorithmic recommendation systems an integral part of how users navigate, consume, and evaluate content. Whether in e-commerce or social media environments, these systems do more than just personalize content — they take an active role in shaping emotions, guiding attention, and swaying public debates around convenience, precision, safety, ethics and visibility.

Currently, research in this field predominantly focuses on quantitative studies examining consumers’ perception (Dodeja et al., 2023), acceptance and trust (Lu & Zhang, 2025; Wang et al., 2024) of AI-generated recommendations, including products, services and the virtual characters (Alboqami, 2023; Baudier et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2024) that provide services, as well as influenced consumer behaviors (Markovitch et al., 2024) and decision-making process (Chang & Park, 2024). In the field of AI and computational mathematics integration, Manjre et al. (2024) investigates the synergy between artificial intelligence’s data-driven approaches and computational mathematics’ logical models to improve problem-solving capabilities across various scientific domains. Meanwhile, Lindbäck (2023) develops a fast algorithm applicable to large-scale computational optimal transport problems. Bojic (2024) assesses the extent to which the academic community focuses on the critical issues in recommendation systems and the alignment between these discussions and technological breakthroughs. In addition to academic literature reviews, qualitative studies have also examined issues such as consumers’ trust in AI-driven recommendations, the demands imposed on online communities, and their perceptions thereof. Through in-depth interviews, Rohden and Zeferino (2022) investigates how consumers’ trust can mediate the uncertainty

associated with recommendation systems by alleviating the adverse effects of risk perception. In relation to the dimensions of community structure and cultural dynamics, Bock et al. (2024) conduct interviews to investigate young people's expectations of community groups in the new era, as well as their thoughts under the hypothetical scenario of decelerated technological advancement.

While algorithmic recommendation systems are often discussed in terms of personalization and efficiency, however, there remains a notable lack of understanding consumers' emotional responses and ethical concerns, as well as the longitudinal effects of AI development on consumers' emotional and cognitive evolution. These reactions and feedback are aggregated in textual form within social media posts and community discussions, continuously shaping the perceptions and responses of both participants and new audiences, while also being relayed back to the developers and proprietors of digital platforms. This gap is particularly relevant given the increasing role of non-human agents (e.g., algorithms) in structuring everyday digital interactions; Meanwhile, human participants—including internet users, web developers, platform owners, and advertisers—are shaping the behaviors of other stakeholders based on their respective interests, thereby forming an interconnected behavioral network. Especially within community-organized networks, the exploration of such conversations and interactions remains notably limited. In particular, this study intends to utilize Kozinets' (2020) netnography theory for further research, to explore consumer discourses and online activities in the AI interaction domain.

Drawing on platform studies and socio-technical theories, scholars, such as Latour, van Dijck, and Beer, have argued that algorithmic recommendation systems are not neutral tools, but 'actors' embedded in complex assemblages that include human users, platform protocols, and cultural expectations. These assemblages co-produce meanings, behaviors, and power relations across digital contexts. This thesis addresses previous mentioned gap, while also considering both human and non-human participants that are often overlooked, by exploring in what ways do users articulate their perspectives and attitudes toward the increasingly prevalent intelligent recommendation systems through various forms of discourse in contemporary platform environments; and by asking: *How do users' mindsets and emotional responses to AI recommendations contribute to the development of review cultures and online communities?*

Positioned at the intersection of consumer psychology and behavioristics, platform study, artificial intelligence technology, and marketing communication, this research addresses emerging opportunities and unresolved challenges highlighted by recent academic advancements in these interconnected fields. Concurrently, this study seeks to investigate community activities and content generation culture within the AI context, thereby highlighting the uniqueness and heterogeneity of these phenomena to relevant industry professionals. The article proceeds as follows: after reviewing relevant literature, it presents the theoretical framework and methodological approach. The content focuses on aspects such as elucidating the rationale behind selecting Actor-Network Theory (ANT) as the theoretical framework; examining the academic and practical implications of integrating ANT with netnography methodology; and justifying the selection of two major social media platforms as the primary analytical domains for this research. The remaining part is followed by an analysis of online data, and concludes with a discussion of implications for both theory and platform study.

2. Literature review

2.1 Recommendation Systems as Agents of Platform Power

Platforms and recommendation systems

Gillespie (2010) draws upon the definition of ‘platform’ provided in the Oxford English Dictionary and explicates its connotations from four perspectives: computational, architectural, figurative, and political. ‘Platform’ is abstracted as an elevated horizontal plane, aiming to provide more convenient support for subsequent activities. While it is anticipatory in nature, it does not establish causality. Furthermore, it conveys a neutral stance toward the activities, though this neutrality may vary depending on contextual factors. Scholars, represented by Castells, consider platforms and digital networks as embodiments of the power dynamics between institutional producers and individual consumers from the political-economic perspective. His ideas go straight to the institutional level of power wielding. Castells (2009) argues that the emergence of Web 2.0 arises from the imbalance between users’ pursuit of communication freedom, and the constraints imposed by owners. The concept of platform neutrality advocated by Gillespie is becoming progressively harder

to sustain in light of advancements in modern network technology, whereas the power dynamics highlighted by Castells have grown increasingly pronounced. As Lash (2007) articulates, the pervasive media society signifies a societal shift wherein algorithms increasingly wield power.

As outlined in the introduction of this thesis, recommendation systems have become deeply embedded in our daily lives, serving as an essential component thereof. These systems leverage advanced computational technologies, including big data analytics, machine learning, and artificial intelligence, while incorporating a range of algorithms designed to fulfill diverse objectives (Wang et al., 2024). Bojic (2024) has expanded the specific algorithmic term “recommendation system,” which is commonly referred to as such, to a more comprehensive definition that includes the various algorithm-driven recommendation mechanisms currently prevalent across numerous modern mainstream platforms. Thorat et al. (2015) summarizes three key types of recommendation systems: content-based filtering, which analyzes a user’s past activities to recommend items; collaborative filtering, which generates recommendations using a database of users with similar preferences; and a hybrid model that combines both methods to address their limitations. A recommendation system predicts user preferences among multiple options by applying information filtering techniques. By providing curated options, it simplifies users’ decision-making and improves choice accuracy (Xiao & Benbasat, 2007). Consumer emotions, ethical debates, and review behaviors may, to a certain extent, be transformed into ‘behavioral and profiling’ data that underpin algorithm-driven recommendation systems. Software translates social behaviors into computer language and vice versa. For example, Amazon encodes user preferences and purchases, while LinkedIn maps job seeker and employer networks. Subsequently, these platforms translate these encoded social interactions into algorithmic instructions (or as ‘recommendations’) to influence user behavior.

Algorithms as non-neutral agents shaping attention, desire and choice

By continuously engaging in data collection, data analysis, and leveraging algorithms to encode computational logic for service provision, these digital platforms are progressively enhancing their capabilities in predictive analytics. Predictive analytics allows statisticians to “extract information from all data to capture relationships between variables from past occurrences and the likeliness of users will exhibit such behavior in the future” (van Dijck, 2013, p.162). The crux of platforms lies in their capacity of algorithms for processing data.

Similar to the product recommendations commonly seen on e-commerce platforms, such as “customers who bought this item also bought...”, these suggestions are a direct outcome of algorithmic processing. However, as van Dijck (2013) highlights, the recommendation systems employed by companies such as Amazon not only generate automated outputs, but also signify the integration of algorithm-driven data analysis into social interaction dynamics. This process subsequently translates into commercial strategies. Kozinets et al. (2017) find technology increasing the passion to consume and the effects associated with participation in the network. In essence, the purpose of algorithms extends beyond merely providing recommendations to actively shaping and influencing user preferences and decision-making processes.

After actively or passively consenting to the platform’s provision of such recommendations, users’ latent desires are awakened. Belk et al. (2003) defines consumer desire as a profound yearning that arises in the interplay between the allure of consumption and the complexities of social circumstances. As products of the market economy and social environment, advertising, retail displays, movies, TV programs, and stories told by others, etc., all kinds of means are stimulating people’s fantasies. However, whether it is the consumer decisions mentioned earlier or the consumers’ desires, the most inceptive and fundamental unit of power is ‘attention’, which activates latent desires and significantly shapes consumers’ lifestyles.

From personalization to manipulation

“Customization seems to have become less the art of soliciting customers’ needs than the science of engineering their desires” (van Dijck, 2013, p.170). Metaphorically described, the online activities of netizens nowadays are not merely the result of platforms being set up by net providers; they are rather a deliberate act programmed in. This kind of customized service is like water delivery service, which has transformed from providing pipes to directly delivering a branded mineral water. Although they are essentially all water, in reality, it seems that consumers’ choices and cost options have been severely limited. van Dijck (2013) reveals users prefer diverse content and formats, while platforms prioritize standardized services. Some standardization is key to improving connectivity and its quality. Universal inputs and standardized outputs enhance algorithm efficiency. The author argues that machines are fundamentally not predisposed toward generating highly personalized content.

In the current context where various digital platforms are competing to promote their products or services through algorithms, although they will increasingly provide better purchasing experiences, there are still some issues, for instance, as van Dijck (2013) points out, platforms and advertisers are increasingly rendering user experiences both more manipulable and more marketable. Marketing professionals now can leverage information technology to achieve precise segmentation of consumers. Once this segmentation is successfully implemented, it will substantially improve operational efficiency and lead to a notable increase in revenue (Beer, 2009). Our life experiences, preferences, and personal details, once encoded into machine language, become personal profiles, mailing lists, data, and even markets (Berry & Moss, 2008). With the aid of elaborate user data and sophisticated algorithms, what the platform is going to do next is to expand its user base and enhance user engagement and integrate into users' daily routines (van Dijck, 2013). As Lash (2006) states, data now comes to find us. The phenomena we encounter, along with the experiences and perceptions of the world that arise from them, are all subject to the influence of algorithmic curation and filtration processes. The algorithm is designed to dynamically adjust the content displayed to an individual based on a data-driven personal profile, with the aim of optimizing user interaction. In this context, users are often treated more as means to achieve specific objectives, rather than as the ultimate goal (Bontridder & Pouillet, 2021).

2.2 User Emotions and Review Cultures in Platform Environments

Expression on social media and community dynamics

Kim et al. (2013) conclude that social media platforms play an important role in spreading public information. They also provide online spaces where people can express their opinions. These platforms support diverse forms of user engagement and activity. Users can not only access news and information via these platforms, but also communicate their ideas effectively. The widespread popularity of such platforms has made it possible for online communities to be formed. As noted by Muñiz and O'Guinn (2001), the continuous advancement of technology facilitates the convergence and interaction of geographically dispersed individuals who share common goals and identities. The emergence of mass media has facilitated communities' ability to efficiently disseminate and replicate information. Consequently, community members are able to develop sophisticated cognitive representations of many fellow members they have never encountered in person, and can imagine their existence with vividness. Harris and Abedin (2016) argue online communities

are progressively evolving into platforms for social interaction, political engagement, and business operations. Meanwhile, social media technologies are increasingly integrating into daily routines, redefining the participatory dynamics within online communities and transforming them into a synthesis of societal and technological elements. This feature is also evident in the present study. By conducting an in-depth analysis of the behaviors and cultures of online communities within social media, and leveraging the technological dimensions introduced by the AI theme, this cultural phenomenon—characterized by the integration of sociology and socio-technical studies—reveals enhanced research significance.

Social media as sentiment expression portal

Given that consumers tend to predominantly articulate their opinions and emotions via social media, it has emerged as an important focus of this research. ‘Social’ conveys the messages of ‘interactivity’ and ‘participatory’, and social media can be conceptualized as online instruments that facilitate or strengthen human networks, thereby promoting the social value of connectedness (van Dijck, 2013). Personal ideas, values, and preferences exhibit a degree of contagion and spread through interpersonal networks; simultaneously, these networks exert an influence on what individuals do and think (Christakis & Fowler, 2009). Papacharissi (2009) comparatively analyzes different platforms demonstrating how the architectural designs of various websites influence distinct patterns of connectedness, styles of self-presentation, and expressions of taste.

2.3 Ethical Debates and Algorithmic Governance

Ethical debates constitute a central focus for users in articulating their emotional responses

van Dijck (2013) concludes that the user responses often express concepts such as individuality, privacy, community and identity, which makes them more closely related to the broader debate on information control. This thesis includes ‘ethics’ in its discussion for several reasons. A user’s attitude and emotional response toward digital platform participants can shape their sense of identity. These responses also influence how they behave online. In turn, this may affect whether other users or stakeholders choose to stay or leave the platform. Another reason warranting the exploration of this topic is that, while values and moral standards may possess a degree of universality, the differing interests and demands of various

stakeholders lead to divergent perspectives. For instance, large Internet corporations exemplify this phenomenon by opposing overregulation of the technology sector. They are concerned that this would impede innovation and business investment, and call for opening up to let the market itself regulate (Schmidt & Cohen, 2010). Furthermore, large non-profit organizations such as Bits of Freedom, European Digital Rights, and the Electronic Frontier Foundation, as well as consumer-based organizations like American Center for Digital Democracy, have actively participated in the topic discussions and the formulation of regulations (van Dijck, 2013), making the ethical issues arising from information technology development more prominent. Other phenomena emerging alongside the development of society, such as Poritz's (2007) discussion of collective privacy, have increasingly attracted scholarly attention. This concept has evolved into a complex legal and ethical domain. However, its theoretical infrastructure remains underdeveloped, creating open spaces for regulation and protection. As technology advances, users' thoughts and discussions evolve, and awareness of rights and freedoms grows. This is evident from both academic discourse and user expressions in this study.

Tensions between community ethics and platform monetization

Since the early Web 2.0 was designed to create connections, build communities and enhance network democracy, it attracted many users who were eager to gain connectedness (van Dijck, 2013). Web 2.0 is a concept that describes a major transformation on a large scale, towards a 'participatory' and 'collaborative' version of the web (Beer, 2009, p.986), where users could generate content. However, as mainstream online platforms have been imbued with commercial attributes, these companies have shifted their focus from community building to the collection of user data. Moreover, connectivity is now perceived as a valuable resource, which engineers encode into algorithms to generate revenue (van Dijck, 2013).

Social media platforms not only continuously fulfill the demands and expectations of their stakeholders, but also adapt to the advancements of competitors and the evolution of broader economic and technological infrastructures (Feenberg, 2009). As van Dijck (2013) states, under the continuous development of information technology in recent years, the word 'social' represents: technologically manageable and economically exploitable. Similarly, the architecture of platform systems is designed to regulate user agency, as most platform proprietors are highly motivated to ascertain users' 'authentic' identities, preferences, and behavioral data (Baym, 2020). However, it is crucial to emphasize that monetization

strategies should not be conceptualized as static exploitation frameworks, rather, as dynamic mediators that actively influence and regulate the processes of shaping sociality and fostering creativity (van Dijck, 2013). Therefore, the author argues that monetization is significantly impacting both the content innovation and community relationships of platform users.

In a sense, significant transformations are occurring in the nature of ecosystems and online social interactions, encompassing the role of algorithms in shaping desires, users' agency over their data, the tension between community-oriented connectedness and commercially driven connectivity, as well as the evolving definitions of 'public' and 'non-public' domains (van Dijck, 2013). As "people making connections and constructing communities is a necessary pretext for manipulating and monetizing social data" (van Dijck, 2013, p.162), this necessarily entails this thesis to analyze the role of people as 'actors' and their corresponding actions within social systems.

The power of the filter bubble and users' resistance

Pariser (2011) argues that the dynamics of personalization and customization creates so-called 'filter bubbles': algorithms may create information determinism, where past clickstreams dictate our future, making us controllable (Bontridder & Pouillet, 2021). This trend not only diminishes users' capacity for rational decision-making, but also impairs their ability to access information effectively. Beer (2009) states that this represents an exercise of power. It is not about the direct power of one individual over another, but rather the software autonomously making decisions and forming connections on behalf of users, which in turn shapes their everyday experiences. This issue is one of the main focuses of this research. It examines users' concerns when they recognize and resist the filter bubble phenomenon.

3. Theoretical framework

3.1 ANT in Digital Research: Reassembling the Social

This thesis has drawn significant theoretical inspiration from Actor-Network Theory (ANT) by Bruno Latour. He examines the foundations of social science and dedicates to redefining the concept of 'social'. Latour challenges the customs of social scientists to attribute stabilized and definitive meanings to 'social' when they are analyzing phenomena, contending that this materialistic approach is likely to generate new problems. The social

world is not only constituted by stable entities, established affiliations, and fixed categories, but also shaped by dynamic processes of ‘the assembled’ that enable “define the new associations that they have been forced to establish” (Latour, 2005, p.12).

Latour’s point of departure for deconstructing the established order of social science lies in recognizing controversies and ‘feeding off controversies’. He argues that the foundation for creating a new order is to acknowledge controversies, rather than focusing solely on how to settle or resolve them. In the network relationships that constitute this new form of ‘association’, participants are reexamined and redefined, integrating both human and non-human roles into the scope of discussion. His greatest theoretical contribution lies in reversing the logic that sociologists previously used to distinguish between objects and humans based on their “incommensurability”. Instead, he states that it’s precisely because of this incommensurability that objects must be treated as legitimate research subjects. This insight is significant for this research in that it highlights how algorithms, machine-generated content and recommendations influence and shape interactions with platform users across various digital platforms in fundamentally incommensurable ways.

3.2 Latour’s Theories and Its Significance to This Research

It must be acknowledged that continuous social movements are not only rooted in the interactions among humans and the connections among objects, but also in the ongoing ‘zigzag’ between these two domains. From the socio-technical point of view, ANT doesn’t view platforms as mere artifacts but as a series of relationships that must be continuously enacted. It is through the diverse ‘actors’ involved that attribute meaning to the platform. Building on this theoretical foundation, the present study also places emphasis on this aspect as a key focus of investigation. The author draws on ANT’s expansive definition of actors to include both human (e.g., users, reviewers, developers) agents and non-human elements (e.g., recommendation algorithms, platform interfaces, content moderation systems). These actors participate in shaping platform experiences and producing emotional and ethical effects in user interactions.

Latour (2005) also states that traditional sociology posits a social aggregation process involving few mediators and many intermediaries. In contrast, ANT theory suggests that such aggregations should encompass innumerable mediators. Within the activities of new associations, non-human objects continuously shift between the roles of mediators and intermediaries. ANT’s philosophical meaning insists that intermediaries ‘transport’ a cause,

while “there exist translations between mediators that may generate traceable association” (Latour, 2005, p108). When actors are no longer seen as mere intermediaries, but instead function as active mediators, they don’t simply ‘transport’ unaltered. Rather, they may become the source of new ‘translations’. In ANT, a platform serves as a mediator rather than a mere intermediary: it actively shapes the expression of social behaviors instead of simply facilitating. Consequently, through this transformative process, the ‘social’ may cease to be constituted by the outdated assemblage that was previously considered integral to the society. This theory is crucial for this research in positioning AI recommendations as significant participants. By reframing algorithms and machine-generated content not merely as objects or tools, but as active entities embedded in the lives of internet users, we can reassess their role as agents shaping cognition, dialogue, and behavior. Investigating the performances and transformations they enact enables us to observe and understand the online world from a genuinely egalitarian perspective, moving beyond a hierarchical and dominantly observational stance.

It’s also worth noting that Latour incorporated the metaphor of the ‘black box’ into the discussion on ‘mediators’ and ‘intermediaries’. Given the distinct modes of information transmission and processing within the ‘black box’ for these two concepts, greater emphasis has been placed on examining the intermediate stages. In the AI-dominated digital era, it is timely to investigate the algorithmic black boxes. Most recommendation systems do not provide users with clear insights into the system logic or recommendation rationale. This lack of transparency intensifies the black box problem, which refers to the growing complexity and challenges in interpreting modern artificial intelligence systems (Zednik, 2021). It is worth noting that we are not only reassessing humanity morally, but also including non-human entities in this discussion. Regardless of our initial intentions or qualities, history shows that non-human entities have gained knowledge, capabilities, values, and ethical dimensions through information technology development. “The sum of morality does not only remain stable but increases enormously with the population of nonhumans” (Latour, 1992, p.232). Thus, uncovering netizens’ discussions about AI as a non-human entity, examining their debates and evaluations, and exploring their value reflections, is key to understanding internet users’ attitudes toward its mediating role. Additionally, such an investigation significantly contributes to research on how these voices shape and influence the community ecology within the internet environment.

Another significant contribution by Latour is his re-interpretation of the concept of “network”. Newman (2003) summarizes that a network consists of a set of items, commonly referred to as vertices or nodes, which are connected by links known as edges. Networks can be physical technical networks-internet or transportation, and can also be connections and relations between individuals and organizations. In the second context, network reflects Granovetter’s (1985) delineation that it represents an informal way of associating human agents. Castells (2000) innovatively consolidates the two meanings together because of the development of information technology. Akrich (1992) states that technical objects participate in creating heterogeneous networks which bring together all kinds of actors, no matter if they are human or nonhuman. In the contextual discussion of ANT, network is “a tool to help describe something, not what is being described” (Latour, 2005, p131). In this study’s observation of various participants, or ‘actors’, within digital platforms, a network can be understood as the trace left behind by a moving agent. In the milieu of ‘social’ within the digital realm, our focus should not be only on the various entities or virtual objects themselves, but rather on what travels among these entities, what calibrates their relationships, and what potentially establishes a degree of commensurability between them. We must not overlook the momentous structural inertia nor underestimate the substantial internal fluidity. In a sense, it is precisely this internal fluidity that has enabled the system to achieve relative stability. Traditional sociologists characterize this power relation as an asymmetry within a state of dynamic equilibrium. In contrast, ANT guides this research not engaged in extensive debate on this matter, but instead, emphasizing the importance of ‘follow the actors’. ANT provides a way to move beyond human-centered models of consumption and explore how algorithmic recommendation systems act as mediators in digital environments — shaping user experiences, emotions, and ethical debates through dynamic socio-technical networks.

It’s essential to disassemble each platform as a social-technological construct and trace the actions of both human and non-human actors, to examine how they leverage tools to shape social practices. Referring to Latour (2005) reassembling the social at the same time, we know that merely disassembling platforms is insufficient. We also need to reassemble the collaborative platform ecosystem in order to identify the norms and mechanisms that underpin networked sociality and creativity. The ongoing evolution of social norms is also reconfiguring the operational dynamics of social networking platforms. Only by considering

the broader cultural matrix within which these assemblages are embedded, can a connective approach achieve success.

4. Methodology

4.1 Netnography

This study adopts Kozinets' concept of netnography, a qualitative research method that differs from traditional ethnography. Netnography seeks to investigate and interpret cultural experiences embedded in the traces, practices, networks, and systems of social media. These cultural experiences can be engaged with, communicated through, and reflected upon (Kozinets, 2020). As a naturalistic and unobtrusive research method, netnography provides "information on the symbolism, meanings, and consumption patterns of online consumer groups" (Kozinets, 2002, p.61). The elements of investigation and immersion serve as key approaches in this study. Traditional ethnography involves active participation and systematic observation within a specific cultural context, alongside the acknowledgment and utilization of the researcher's reflexivity. To an extent, its effectiveness relies on the acuity of the researcher as an instrument (Sherry, 1991). Netnography, like ethnography, is inherently flexible and can align with the interests and skill sets of individual marketing researchers. It also incorporates the research steps of ethnography, albeit with some differences in emphasis (Kozinets, 2002).

Netnography allows this study to observe and interpret the cultural and emotional dimensions of user engagement with AI recommendations in naturalistic online settings. It enables the tracing of consumer expressions of desire, ethical reflection, and evaluative behavior in real time, across multiple platform contexts. Kozinets summarizes two dimensions of data attributes: one is data directly extracted from computer-mediated communication among online community members, and the other is data recorded by researchers based on their observations of communities, members, interactions, and meanings. Based on fundamental research observations, adopting an empathetic approach to comprehend the context of the research subject and striving to interpret its underlying connotations are critical determinants that shape the research outcomes. It deserves noting that van Maanen (1988) argues that the classification and coding of data represent critical concerns, as they necessitate a careful balancing act between symbolic richness and conceptual clarity. The author maintains some

reservations here. This is because the author holds the belief that the interpretation of data derived from netnography can serve both to uncover its metaphorical and symbolic dimensions, and to facilitate categorization, thereby enabling a better grasp of the attitudes and perspectives of different social or cultural groups.

4.2 Following Actors, Tracing Mediators and Analyzing Controversies

Goffman (1990) elucidates the dynamic interplay of self-presentation and impression management that individuals get into across diverse social contexts, drawing a vivid analogy to ‘actors’ performing on a stage. Actors engaging in interactions on the social media examined in this article may not actively switch between different social roles. Nevertheless, their role definitions and mutual influences warrant thorough observation and analysis. Castells (2009) identifies the designated social actors that serve as the primary wielders of power within the societal framework. The struggle in the platform is headed by ‘programmers’, the ones designing networks and platforms; and ‘switchers’, the ones connecting and coordinating different networks; and of course, the ones who hold the most power are the platform owners and advertisers. While, the majority of users constitute the largest proportion in terms of volume in platforms, they are recipients and consumers, producers and participants of culture; they may be considered amateurs and citizens as well as professionals and laborers (van Dijck, 2009). Platforms such as YouTube, which function as cultural intermediaries, represent a complex and precarious endeavor, due to the need to serve multiple stakeholders, including end users, advertisers, and professional content creators.

Akrich and Latour (1992) states that an actor refers to an agent assigned with a role, typically anthropomorphized, through which they enact specific actions or behaviors within a defined context. This feature is particularly apt for the roles of digital platforms that possess both human and nonhuman actors. Within the digital platform participants examined in this thesis, algorithm-driven recommendations can be considered as embodying a non-human platform role. However, we can not simply analyze it as a machine for the reason that it is not merely a machine. Engineers are the ‘authors’ of subtle plots and scenarios and interlocking characters, granting the non-human roles with figurative image.

The theoretical framework constructed based on Actor-Network Theory (ANT) informs the netnographic approach by guiding attention to both human and non-human actors in the platform assemblage — from users and reviewers to algorithms, platform interfaces, and recommendation prompts. By integrating Actor-Network Theory with netnography, this research is situated within the framework of platform studies, offers novel theoretical insights and methodological approaches to community interaction and review culture. Furthermore, in the socio-technical domain, particularly in algorithmic research centered on user contexts, it achieves significant advancements in comprehending comment mechanisms and the socio-digital influence of online communities. Following the actors, the author examines how these entities co-produce meaning, emotion, and ethical stances in user-generated content. To interpret user interactions, this thesis uses interpretive strategies from discourse and narrative approaches, integrated into a netnographic method that emphasizes situated cultural meaning-making across platforms. Whether regarding netnography or other methods, a critical fact remains: human actors' conversations, comments, and interactions are observable and easier to analyze. In contrast, non-human actors' activities remain constrained. Specifically, real-time machine responses are still largely pre-programmed by the developers. This observation highlights the need to examine the limitations of machines as research subjects. Latour has a very interesting expression on this: “machines are not talking actors, not because they are unable to do so, but because they might have chosen to remain silent to become agreeable to their fellow machines and fellow humans”(Latour, 1992, p.249).

4.3 Platform Selection and Data Collection

Trendy social media embraces the values and principles: popularity, growth, traffic, turnover, and personalization. In selecting the research platform for this study, the following criteria were primarily considered: (1) Platforms with focused and relevant websites, topics, or groups that feature machine-recommended services or enable natural user interactions; (2) Prioritizing posts (no matter from which side of the participants) with higher traffic and greater levels of interactive engagement; (3) A larger number of independent contributors; (4) Content that is detailed, richly descriptive, and capable of conveying authentic narratives and activities; (5) Platforms employing a chronological cascading layout, allowing for longitudinal observation of behavioral changes among human and non-human participants across different time periods. It is evident that three critical dimensions emerge as key factors: the free expression of users, well-developed comment and interaction systems, and mature online communities.

Thus, this study concentrates on data collection from two major social media platforms, which are Facebook and Reddit. Facebook (n.d.) states itself as a platform designed to help people build community. Due to the existence of numerous influential communities on Facebook that focus on AI technology and its latest development achievements, the author applied to join these communities as an observer, specifically looking for content related to AI recommendation systems. Reddit is a social media platform and online community where registered users can submit content to discussion boards categorized by themes (referred to as “subreddits”), such as text posts, pictures and videos. On Reddit, the author directly targets and searches for the attitudes and emotional responses of platform users towards AI recommendations, in order to observe the ecological reactions within the community.

Furthermore, the author selects social media platforms as the carriers for studying public opinions on related recommendation systems. The main considerations are as follows: In real life, even if users have experienced algorithmic recommendations on different platforms and made purchases or other actions, their evaluations and opinions on these experiences are often not confined to the platform itself (for instance, users may complete purchases due to product recommendations from Amazon, but their sharing of shopping experiences may not necessarily be reflected in product reviews). In contrast, trendy social media platforms, with their high daily active user volume, rich content ecosystem, and highly concentrated community sharing characteristics, not only provide users with a more open expression space, but also facilitate the conduct of this research and data collection more conveniently.

This thesis has selected and analyzed a total of 170 posts. Specifically, 50 posts were collected and examined from 5 Facebook communities (which are: All About AI Tools & AI News; SaaS AI Tools - AI for Entrepreneurs, Creators, Marketers, and Founders; AI for Business & Life; AI Tools 101 - Trending AI Tools & Prompts and AI: Artificial Intelligence); 120 posts were systematically identified on Reddit through targeted searches using the keyword “recommendation system” for relevant topic discussions. During the process of content and discourse analysis, the author also focused on user interactions and discussion trends, which facilitated a better knowledge in review culture and community dynamics. All research materials were published between January 2020 and April 2025. In organizing the data, the author tries to arrange them chronologically to effectively illustrate the temporal changes in user behavior.

5. Findings

5.1 When Algorithms Function as Non-human Mediators

In the comments on Facebook groups and discussions on Reddit, the author notes that commenters viewed algorithms and intelligent recommendation systems as active agents within the contemporary Internet ecosystem. More precisely, they function as mediators (according to ANT theories) rather than mere participants, as these non-human actors not only convey information to users, but also engage in extensive “translation,” striving to maximize their influence.

For instance, it is indicated by users that the recommendation systems of various platforms are attempting to influence an individual’s aesthetic preferences. Algorithms have vastly undermined the enjoyment associated with this process. As Reddit user Thezonehero said, “I don’t need an AI to mediate my relationship with art. I’m not trying to min-max anything. I’m just trying to connect with life and other human beings.” Furthermore, some users contend that algorithms incorporate excessive marketing elements. They noted that many artists invest in promoting their works through algorithm-driven recommendations to enhance their visibility. Oneinternetperson shared his/her experience on this, “Spotify’s algorithm sucks. For example, I have ~100 jimmy-eat-world songs in my playlist and 5 taylor swift songs in it. When I shuffle, it’s almost guaranteed that I will hear 2 taylor swift’s songs before I hear one jimmy’s song, and they aren’t even a super niche band. ”

In Facebook groups like “AI: Artificial Intelligence,” users debate whether AI can develop empathy or self-awareness. While some emphasize the convenience of intelligent recommendations, others argue these systems oversimplify or mislabel personal identities. Users have reported troubling cases of incorrect categorization. A netizen named Rectile said, “They seemed to label me with a single, hyper homogenized sub-genre of bro-metal and decided that it was all I would hear until I die. I hated it.” What is even more concerning is the case of a netizen called impressive50, who finds it highly unacceptable for platforms to deliberately speculate on users’ identities, family backgrounds, and personal circumstances, “I think it’s misogyny to figure out someone as in a ‘normal’ family background and surely having family and children. Based on the recommendation, I’m a very wise mother, who bred childs and is a bit sorrowful occasionally, like a sensitive girl, and lost someone recently desperately. The worst thing is they guess I long for a macho guy (not at all my fancy) who is

a bit stupid and old fashioned.... What the f... hah! phenomenal unmatched! I'm in this category (in terms of social gender) web marketer's conventional thinking..."

Online discourse highlights how users ascribe personalities or intentions to AI systems. Some characterize AI as overly controlling, others as useful yet limited tools. These personifications reflect deeper cultural narratives about automation, capitalism, and control. Amid intense debates about algorithms employed by various platforms, many users have critiqued the performance of these algorithms. For instance, some argue that Spotify's algorithms are overly conservative, prioritizing 'safe' over innovation, while others question Apple Music's focus on niche and novelty in its recommendations.

An interesting observation is that, even within the community, although most people are cautious about data collection, there are indeed users who have expressed that they would actively provide feedback on some of the latest intelligent recommendation technologies or related services. A Facebook user named macguy, shared that he/she hopes the technology can keep innovating and breaking through, so that he/she can enjoy better products and services. Many people also liked his/her comment. Some individuals also reported their participation in the internal testing initiatives of certain platforms, delivering a thorough knowledge of user preferences. These participants demonstrated a willingness to invest effort towards enhancing product quality. This also reflects that some users hope AI, as a "mediator," can have greater capabilities to improve the convenience and quality of people's digital lives.

5.2 The Network Constructed Around AI Recommendations

The network relationships among different participants around the intelligent recommendation system are gradually revealed through specific topics. This involves discussions about the capabilities and influence of non-human actors, debates on rules and regulations in the broad circle, and the phenomenon where users gain benefits or even economic returns. At the same time, some users experience negative emotions or are injected with negative energy due to the influence of the system. The existence of multiple interactive relationships makes these network structures both vibrant and in a state of continuous dynamic evolution.

In a discussion regarding the quality of content recommendations following AI-based consultations, users raised concerns about the adequacy of current recommendation systems.

Nevertheless, some users appreciate AI suggestions for their convenience. For instance, a Reddit user named Note expressed: “I don’t think there is less value in AI recommendations. I treat them the same as being recommended for something online. I’m not sure why there are some people who think it will turn you into a mindless sheep, or whatever, it’s just another source of recommendations I think.” Some netizens also expressed that these recommendations have helped him/her a lot to some extent, because he/she only wants to enjoy music itself and not spend a lot of time “exploring music”. Interestingly, many netizens shared their views, stating that they regarded TikTok as a role model for intelligent recommendation, attributing its success to its outstanding algorithm recommendation capabilities. The netizens said that in addition to respecting and praising the content of independent media, TikTok is also good at handling community connections and tag management, which makes most users feel that even if they receive advertising content, the vast majority of the content is about topics they are interested in.

Owing to the diverse policies concerning data collection and privacy protection across various regions, users from different areas may exhibit differing emotional responses towards related issues. For example, EU-based users (as noted by the commenter) have articulated their trust in the data collection practices within the European Union. Nevertheless, the ensuing debates and disagreements have caused tensions and conflicts within communities that emerge during discussions on this subject. Disputes and discussions among human actors caused by non-human actors such as “algorithms”, “platform policies”, and “laws and regulations” have formed a complex network of responsibility parties, and similar models are not rare on platforms.

Human actors are also discussing how to deal with the “invasion” of their working and living spaces by non-human actors. In the Facebook “AI: Artificial Intelligence” group, a member started a discussion thread expressing concerns about reading AI-recommended news or interacting with AI systems, fearing these technologies might replace human roles. Many commenters agreed, with some even sharing vivid “apocalypse”-themed nightmares. Others argued that certain professions may remain unaffected. For example, one participant, Paul remarked, “By the time I requested the system to execute the 4th revision of an idea, I realized that my expertise and involvement are still in the game.” Michael expressed: “‘Adaptation or death’ is the most realistic assessment here... If we consider AI recommendations as ‘auxiliary intelligence’, then we remain ‘intelligent’ while the machine is merely ‘assistant’... When this relationship is reversed, problems would arise.” In depth

discussions on intelligent recommendations are growing. User Nit noted that while “intelligent recommendation” shows intelligence, it lacks consciousness, as machines only mimic human thinking. This sparked a two-sided debate in the community (AI: Artificial Intelligence): some believe machines could surpass human intelligence through development, while others agree that giving machines consciousness and self-awareness is highly challenging and may not be fully achievable..

While a big number of users engage in jest and comparison regarding the intelligent recommendation services offered by various music and video platforms, some discussions also involve users seeking or recommending high-quality third-party software or plugins. As some of them state, these tools assist in filtering and optimizing recommendation functions to better align with individual usage expectations. The opposing behavior involves users explicitly indicating their preference to no longer receive similar services. For example, on the YouTube Music platform, users can click “No longer recommend” for content suggested by the intelligent recommendation system. Nevertheless, such functionality appears ineffective, as numerous users have reported in discussions that despite repeatedly selecting this option to decline similar recommendations, the platform continues to deliver analogous content. Different network participants continuously interact and negotiate “commensurability” in these ongoing interactions, striving to reach a balanced state that can meet each other’s needs.

Some individuals have expressed concerns that, regardless of the apparent sophistication of intelligent recommendation systems, these systems frequently struggle to adapt to shifts in users’ interests and preferences, resulting in a notable delay. Despite the differing opinions regarding which music platform boasts a superior intelligent recommendation function, some users argue that only through prolonged usage and consistent feedback can the platform refine its recommendations to better suit individual preferences, even some people used the word “manipulation” in their discourse. Otherwise, the recommendations may exhibit the inconsistency often noted by users, characterized as “frequent oscillation” between different platforms. However, there are still quite a number of users who cannot completely abandon the services provided by some platforms, and they have also had enough of the repetitive and annoying intelligent recommendation content. Therefore, they have no choice but to re-establish their accounts, interact with machines again, or train the intelligent recommendation system to provide the content they want.

Interestingly, some users have come to view their experience in fine-tuning algorithms as an intangible asset. Some have even gone so far as to establish subscription-based services aimed at attracting individuals who are genuinely frustrated by algorithmic recommendations yet remain reliant on these platforms. This phenomenon reflects the emergence of a “knowledge economy” in the community wherein such expertise is monetized. These mentioned tensions reflect a broader struggle over user agency — some feel empowered by the mechanisms; others see them as ineffective or symbolic. The active and passive positions of different human actors in negotiating “commensurability” also emerged in similar interactions.

In the meantime, users actively engage in real-time interpretation and evaluation of the information associated with recommended content. For example, a user reported receiving a software recommendation labeled as “You might be interested” within an application store. Upon actual use, the individual found the product to be of extremely poor quality. Consequently, he/she questioned the authenticity of the figure “27k,” which was presented by the intelligent recommendation system to indicate the number of downloads for this product. Additionally, the user expressed skepticism regarding the preferences of these 27k users, reflecting a critical perspective rooted in “cultural capitalism”. It can thus be seen that the focus of the “controversy” is not only between human and non-human actors, but also among human participants, where value judgments exist. The commensurability among them also constitutes a part of the overall network.

5.3 Network ‘Turbulence’

The network that has gradually formed around intelligent recommendation systems is not entirely stable. The derived problems to some extent are striving for it to make judgments and choices to maintain a dynamic balance. For instance, some users argue that as algorithms increasingly tailor recommendations to individual preferences, this may result in individuals being confined to an “echo chamber,” which poses long-term risks. Reddit user Loudhale said: “yep, just the stuff it throws up on the main page is... so many new channels with such obscure names that I’ve not heard of but with familiar samey topics... and it’s all just gotta feeling a bit weird and unreal....shaped, blinkered...really like echo chamber. God knows how much worse this kind of thing will get, now the AI beast has been officially unleashed...” Conversely, others contend that such concerns are overstated, as there are multiple avenues in

daily life through which one can acquire diverse knowledge. Ultimately, the key factor lies in one's attitude rather than the content recommended by the system.

Privacy protection is also an unavoidable topic. A Reddit user named Ghostpower expressed this view: "Data collection/privacy is becoming a mainstream concern. They could be adding noise to their algorithmic system deliberately, to let us come to our own conclusion that the convenience of being served services is worth the trade off of our privacy. The plausible deniability would benefit them more than a defiant approach." Some users with negative perspectives have stated that consumers are, in fact, not merely recipients of services but are themselves the products—entities that generate revenue for platforms. A deactivated user shared, "Privacy has become a myth!" He/She felt that even when he/she shared a meme with friends on Instagram, the merchants were collecting his information and using it. Furthermore, some argue that from the platform's standpoint, consumers are essentially data whose primary function is to drive revenue generation. Similar discussions also sparked in-depth conversations among netizens about films and TV series, such as the appearance of analogous scenes in "Black Mirror." This led some netizens to express panic and share their thoughts.

5.4 User Resistance as Network Negotiation

Recommendations related to investments, particularly those involving cryptocurrencies, tend to evoke a higher degree of skepticism among many individuals (The main analysis and reference were made based on the discussions of the Facebook group "AI: Artificial Intelligence", which has 3.4 million members as of April, 2025). In addition, objectors argue that AI-driven recommendations focus mainly on superficial tasks, lacking deep consulting agency as humans. However, some users share that algorithm-suggested content meets their needs. But some individuals have advocated for the machines' perspective, asserting that the value of such human-machine interactions lies in ensuring that "users are heard and acknowledged." Some users post concerns about inconsistent recommendations for the same query at different times. Others argue that overfitted algorithms reduce the system's usefulness. And some users find current recommendation systems too simplistic. As shared, on the Disney Video platform, if you have watched "Star Wars", it will hilariously recommend other films related to all kinds of "war" films for you. A Reddit user called NULL says the algorithm is "overfitted", as he or she mentioned, the advertisements or video recommendations that he or she sees are almost all things that he or she has already searched

for. After he or she has collected something online, the same product is repeatedly recommended. All these make him or her feel annoyed.

Shared experiences often spark community discussions, where users compare, critique, and joke about recommendation systems. On Reddit, many users criticize platforms like Spotify and YouTube for over-promoting popular artists or failing to get detailed preferences. Some users avoid interacting with AI to prevent unwanted recommendations, while others try to “train” the algorithms despite finding it slow and frustrating. User Alex said: “When I say ‘less’, AM (Apple Music) just keeps forcing it down my throat. It feels like Apple wants to change my tastes at all costs. I hate it.” This reflects AI recommendations can easily annoy users. After some users complained about Facebook’s Reels and ads, other netizens suggested turning off these features in settings. Many also recommended simply deleting the app for convenience.

In the Facebook group “All About AI Tools & AI News,” users reported frequent recommendations for fortune-telling and “transmutation” items after browsing astrology and “feng shui” content. Many participants stressed that such recommendations should not be trusted for significant life decisions. This reflects a relatively conservative trust level among users toward algorithmic recommendations networks, with deeper relationships requiring time to develop.

One Facebook user asked why he/she no longer receives Meta AI services. In the comment, many users humorously remarked that this might be a blessing for the poster. These varied emotional responses reflect both resistance and adaptation to AI presence. The frustration and repeated attempts of individual users when confronted with algorithms and programs, the helplessness and anger expressed in a humorous way, as well as the efforts to retrain the algorithms, truly reflect the weakness of the individual in the face of the powerful logic of algorithms and the strength of platforms, further highlighting the inequality of power among different network subjects.

Apart from expressing their annoyance at the tiresome data collection and questioning classification by AI, many netizens also feel that such recommendations are lagging and erroneous. As they expressed, when you have already purchased a washing machine, it is obvious that you no longer need it, but the algorithm doesn’t think so; when you search for “baby baptism”, it doesn’t mean that you are a woman with a child. Indeed, some individuals

are hesitant to like or interact on social media due to concerns about data collection and frustration with relentless intelligent recommendations. However, at the same time, the absurdly intelligent recommendations (many of which are presented in the form of screenshots) shared by individuals in the community about their personal experiences have become content that is easy to resonate with and interact with, thus stimulating discussions within the community. Such exchanges create solidarity among users with similar grievances and spark collective resistance or adaptation behaviors.

5.5 Platforms as Affective Infrastructures

Users commonly experience frustration, amusement, and even anxiety in response to algorithmic content on platforms. Among opposing voices, there are some that use rather extreme words. For instance, on the Reddit platform's YouTube Music community, there was a user who posted to serve as a "vent thread", in which the words used included referring to the platform's recommended content as "trash", the endless daily push notifications as "electronic diarrhea", and the entire artist's living environment online as being like staying in the "sewer" recommended by AI. Nevertheless, there are voices expressing their positive attitude and expectations towards algorithmic technology, as user Keikam put it: "People don't understand that algorithms are not magic. They won't cater to everyone a hundred percent. Besides, it takes time to adapt. Some genre preferences are going to work better."

Parodic creation of paintings or memes represents an essential component of community communication, often exhibiting enhanced engagement and sharing potential on platforms. In the image shared in the Facebook group "AI: Artificial Intelligence," users employ a quasi-sarcastic tone to satirize concerns surrounding AI technology. Simultaneously, some individuals speculate that such scenarios may not be entirely implausible as future realities. [u/ChurrosComics \(2024\)](#) depicted the current online life in the form of creative comic strips. Whenever you browse or interact with a photo or video, the next day you will receive a flood of related push notifications. Many netizens thus deeply resonated with this post, and shared their own experiences in the comments.

@CHURROSCOMICS

(u/ChurrosComics, 2024. Recommendation System Trap)

Apart from application software, netizens said that even the input method has an intelligent recommendation function. Some instant messaging software will directly generate reply suggestions based on the user's chat context. This has led netizens to make deep complaints and question that such recommended content might make communication and interaction itself not sincere at all. They openly acknowledged that if individuals were to communicate in this manner, it would essentially equate to interaction between robots, devoid of genuine human connection. Some users say the apps are just mimicking natural responses shaped by data. But some other users shared that these services are convenient and time-saving for conversation, making them feel satisfied most of the time. These discussions, particularly those gaining traction, foster an emerging "review culture" where users shape each other's perceptions through sarcasm, humor, and detailed critiques.

Although users' emotional expressions are diverse, the maintenance of online relationships relies on the freedom of participants to express their opinions and emotions. The invisible 'mediator' behind the machines are constantly absorbing information, and trying to adjust the 'turbulence' within the network. This can also be seen in the sharing and discussions among some users about their experiences before and after using certain softwares.

5.6 Network Participants Endeavor to Unravel the “Black Box”

Some users have realized that in many cases, algorithm games are not merely about the algorithmic technology itself. This non-human actor is often a “puppet” manipulated by various interests and influences. Just as user birch expressed on Reddit, “No matter what I play, the next recommendations are just chart music. I can only think they are receiving a lot of serious pocket money, or the guy behind the algorithm thinks all hip hop is the same.” The considerations of market operation personnel regarding their interests and the capabilities and cognitive levels of algorithm engineers were included in the discussion. It seems that this is indeed the case. A user who claimed to be a staff member of YouTube stated that due to the platform receiving a large number of complaints about it recommending too much “radical” content, the algorithm department of the platform has also become more conservative and is more inclined to adjust the algorithm to meet the needs of the majority. As a result, the recommended content appears to be quite conventional.

Some people speculate that the reason why some platforms seem to have imperfect algorithmic recommendation systems is that they have optimized them to maximize their advertising revenue. For instance, on YouTube, click-through rate, retention rate and viewing time are important indicators. If they show you what you want without any distractions or click-bait, you might only watch one video and then leave. This is detrimental to the business. But someone opposes these comments, admitting that if consumers don’t receive the content they want, they might directly leave. “Del” follows: “the first priority now is monetization, not just keeping you hooked for hours. Now they are trying to balance how many ads they could bombard you before you leave.” Some netizens have concluded that the platform’s intelligent recommendation function, which has been critiqued by other users, is becoming increasingly “worse.” However, advertisers have seen vast revenue improvements from this trend. Some users believe creators have become more skilled at crafting clickbait to deceive recommendation engines. A deactivated user offered a political perspective, suggesting left-leaning media institutions are concerned about the consumption of non-mainstream content they find objectionable. As a result, these institutions pressure YouTube to guide users toward mainstream channels rather than allowing unrestricted browsing in the unregulated online “Wild West.” The goal is to prevent access to content which mainstream media seeks to filter out. Additionally, corporate pressures indicate directing users to mainstream channels is more profitable than niche channels with limited financial prospects.

These framings build how users perceive and interact with AI, embedding recommendation systems in broader ideological debates.

The “black box” issue discussed by users is visible and widespread, but different users’ recognition and speculation about it are diverse. All of this seems to stem from the “mystery” maintained by developers and owners regarding the algorithmic recommendation process - or, to put it directly, the opacity of its principles and mechanisms. This opacity has intensified the unequal relationship among participants, and the questioning and criticism have also grown increasingly intense.

Derivative discussions related to the research issues of this thesis also arose within the group, specifically addressing the prevalence of AI-generated music and videos being recommended on streaming platforms. Users’ discussions reflect two extreme perspectives: enthusiasm and disdain. As this thesis focuses solely on users’ responses to intelligent recommendation systems themselves rather than the AI-generated content such as music or videos, we will not delve further into the platform phenomena associated with AI-generated content.

6. Discussion

This chapter examines how users’ mindsets and emotional responses to AI recommendations shape review cultures and foster the development of online communities. Grounded in empirical findings of the previous chapter and informed by Actor-Network Theory (ANT) and netnography, this discussion synthesizes theoretical insights with practical implications.

6.1 Theoretical Implications

This study extends the scenario proposed by Castells (2009), which examines power dynamics between users and platform owners in the Web 2.0 context, to the context of AI recommendation systems. In addition, the findings add value to ongoing theoretical discussions on algorithmic recommendation systems, user agency, and the formation of digital communities as well as the review culture.

This study highlights that emotional responses to algorithmic systems are not just individual affective states, but are shaped and intensified by digital platform architectures. This aligns with scholarship framing platforms as active cultural and affective environments rather than

neutral infrastructures (van Dijck, 2013; Papacharissi, 2009). The analysis demonstrates how emotional ambivalence affects user interactions with AI recommendation systems, particularly when feedback mechanisms are perceived by users as ineffective, or “manipulated”. Such expressions commonly emerge in collective spaces, such as Reddit posts and Facebook groups as this study reflects, where users collaboratively establish critical norms and articulate rebellious sentiments. In this way, the findings enrich theories of affective publics by demonstrating that emotions serve not only as outcomes of technological experiences, but also as mechanisms for forging and contesting communal meaning.

Moreover, the findings shake up the usual models of user agency in algorithmic environments. While some users tried to retrain recommendation systems or develop workarounds, others expressed resignation or emotional exhaustion, revealing a complex mix of empowerment and constraint. This contradicts the simplistic idea of the “empowered user” and supports a more sophisticated comprehension of algorithmic subjectivity, where users operate within a limited sphere influenced by opaque system logic and commercial demands. This lines up with concerns raised by scholars such as Beer (2009) and Bontridder and Poulet (2021), who argue that user behavior is increasingly governed by algorithmic predictions and data profiling, often without full user awareness or consent. These systems effectively ‘nudge’ users toward specific decisions. The present findings contribute empirical depth to these arguments by illustrating how users engage with, negotiate, or emotionally disengage from systems, claiming to know and serve them.

Another key implication pertains to the changing landscape of digital review cultures. As the research data demonstrates, users not only evaluate products or services sold online, but also frequently assess recommendation systems themselves—commenting on their accuracy, transparency, and perceived biases etc.. This reflection indicates that review cultures are becoming increasingly meta-communicative, with users directing their evaluative focus toward the infrastructures creating their consumption experiences. This development corresponds with Kozinets et al. (2017), who conceptualize online consumers as networked agents of cultural production. In this context, reviewing transcends mere preference expression, becoming a political and ethical intervention into the conditions of algorithmic visibility.

This study also identified a growing tension between individuality and identity representation in online communities. Users complain feeling uncomfortable when AI inaccurately

categorizes them, whether as parents, fans, or members of specific groups. These concerns reveal that algorithmic analysis can misidentify individuals in ways that are both inaccurate and socially or morally troubling. This supports the critique that recommendation systems participate in the production of identity categories that may not align with users' self-understandings, thus raising important questions about algorithmic misrecognition and 'filter bubbles' (van Dijck, 2013; Pariser, 2011).

Taken together, these findings point to a set of theoretical implications that extend current debates in digital sociology and platform studies. They affirm the need to conceptualize users not simply as data subjects, but as affectively engaged and reflexively positioned 'actors' who confront algorithmic systems with varying degrees of emotional response. Furthermore, the study serves an emerging literature that sees review practices, emotional discourse, and community interaction as critical sites where the socio-technical boundaries of platforms are continually negotiated. Rather than viewing AI recommendation systems as static technologies or users as passive recipients, this thesis amplifies the relational and contested nature of AI-mediated interaction, shaped by users' emotion, critique, and emergent forms of digital literacy.

6.2 Practical Implications

The findings of this study offer several takeaways with practical relevance for platform designers, developers, and policymakers engaged in shaping AI-mediated digital environments. Based on users' critiques, emotional reactions, and adaptive behaviors as observed in this study, some design and governance considerations emerge that may improve the alignment between AI recommendation systems and the expectations of their users.

One concern repeatedly expressed by users is the ineffectiveness of the current feedback mechanism. For instance, even if they have consistently indicated their disinterest in certain content through clicking the button "not interested" or "no more recommendations", many online users of social media still report that the platforms continue to push similar content to them. This demonstrates that there is a problem with the feedback loop of many platforms, meaning that users' inputs have not been meaningfully processed or reflected in the subsequent algorithm outputs. In response to this, the platform should develop a more transparent and accountable feedback system. These systems should not only allow users to express their preferences, but also enable them to see how their actions affect future

recommendations. Enhancing transparency in this area is in line with the broader trend of explainable AI, as well as regulatory principles such as the EU's General Data Protection Regulation and the proposed framework for artificial intelligence governance.

Another important finding in this study is the issue of personalized fatigue. Many users complained that the current recommendation system was “overfitting”, constantly recommending similar content or items that the user had already consumed or saved, thereby reducing the possibility to see diverse content. This saturation state not only goes against the original intention of the recommendation system, but also leads to emotional resistance among users and potential detachment behaviors. In this regard, platform developers should focus on ensuring the novelty and exploration of the recommended content. It would be best if they could allow users to participate in adjusting the balance of content recommendations, which would help alleviate the rigidity of the recommended content, avoid “filter bubble” and enhance users’ sense of autonomy in the whole experience.

In addition to the above suggestions regarding algorithms and procedures, the author also means to emphasize the affective labor that users undertake when managing their digital environment. As this research has shown, some users re-train algorithms to improve their experience, explore third-party tools within the community; while others express feelings of being wrongly classified by algorithms or being overwhelmed by irrelevant recommendation information, which makes them feel tired and frustrated. Platform owners and managers should recognize this emotional and cognitive labor, making algorithmic processes more responsive while reducing user burden through respectful treatment of users and adaptive system behavior. What’s more, in response to the phenomenon of users being wrongly classified and labeled as mentioned earlier, platforms need to consider adopting a more cautious and ethically sound approach to personalized services. The design of the system should avoid overly simplistic or deterministic identity models, and allow users to correct inaccurate inferences. Additionally, the data training process must focus on diversity of demography and potential biases to prevent the stereotypes.

From a macro perspective, some users attribute their dissatisfaction not only to technical flaws but also to the commercial considerations of the platforms themselves. Many users believe that practices such as maximizing advertising revenue and treating user data as a means to make money actually distort recommendation results and erode user trust. This indicates that the issue is not merely about optimizing intelligent recommendations. To

achieve meaningful change, the entire industry may need to re-examine its business models, including more transparently disclosing commercial interests that influence algorithmic decisions, and exploring governance frameworks that prioritize user well-being over short-term profits. At the same time, government authorities and other regulatory departments should also step in to guide the development of the industry through macro-control measures. The demands made by companies as Schmidt and Cohen (2010) mentioned, which call for the relaxation of regulatory restrictions and advocate allowing market forces to determine user needs, warrant careful and repeated consideration.

At the same time, we could observe that social media platforms play a crucial role in regulating the impact of artificial intelligence on community dynamics. Platform stakeholders must pay attention to issues such as polarization, misinformation, and emotional fluctuations that arise from the improper behavior of recommendation systems on platforms. Additionally, platform stakeholders can also engage with users in social media communities (such as Facebook and Reddit discussion groups mentioned in this thesis) to understand diverse content and implement better feedback mechanisms, which can help curb the formation of the “echo chamber effect” as raised by netizens. Professional mediators can be assigned to similar communities to identify emotional responses and mediate negative discussions caused by intelligent recommendations programs.

6.3 Limitations and Future Research

From a methodological perspective, the reliance on netnographic data collected from Reddit and Facebook communities restricts the generalizability of the findings. The selected platforms primarily serve specific user groups, which may not adequately represent the broader digital audience. Furthermore, the data comprise representative posts and comments chosen by the authors in publicly visible threads, introducing a visibility bias. This bias privileges users who openly express their opinions, who tend to be more critical or emotionally reactive. While this coincides with the emotional responses and themes central to this study, it overlooks potentially important user experiences that are more ambivalent, passive, or silent.

The second limitation is the absence of longitudinal analysis. While some posts were organized chronologically to illustrate changes in users’ emotions, this study did not systematically investigate how users’ attitudes and engagement with the recommendation

system developed over time. Considering the rapid advancements in algorithmic technology in recent years, future research would significantly benefit from long-term tracking of user responses, to better capture emotional shifts and the evolving power dynamics between users and platforms.

This study's sample is mainly from discussions in the English language and the major western platform environments. Thus, it overlooks the variations in user expectations and attitudes toward AI related ethical issues across cultural contexts. Comparative studies in different countries or language environments could offer a more comprehensive knowledge of how algorithmic recommendation systems are developed globally, and help academics explore user behaviors and cultural traits in various places, especially in regions where emerging markets and electronic lifestyles are developing rapidly.

Finally, this study raises thought-provoking questions about user or 'online labor' autonomy in AI-mediated environments, but it does not fully elaborate on the implications of users' multiple roles in AI recommendation systems. Further research could look into how this emerging form of unpaid or affective labor is commodified or exploited within the platform economy.

7. Conclusion

This thesis explores how users respond to algorithmic recommendation systems in online communities, through emotionally charged, reflective, and often ambivalent remarks. Drawing on netnographic data from Reddit and Facebook communities, the study examines how sentiments, such as frustration, sarcasm, resistance, and occasional satisfaction are expressed, shared, and negotiated in relation to AI recommendations. These responses reveal that recommendation systems are not perceived as neutral tools, but as active, and sometimes intrusive "actors" within digital environments. Users are not passive recipients of algorithmic outputs; they interpret, adjust, criticize these systems, and even strategically counter "manipulation".

One important finding of this study is that emotions play a crucial role in users' experience and evaluation of artificial intelligence recommendation systems. The expression of emotions helps to form informal norms, a culture of criticism, and community dynamics. Emotions, as

a structural force in platformized life, shape through expressions of humor, satire, and even anger, indicate what kinds of intelligent recommendation practices are regarded as acceptable, useful, or morally disturbing, in a way that is co-constructed by users.

This study also challenges the current promotion of AI technology empowering users. Although some users actively attempt to train or retrain algorithms, the research found that more people show confusion, fatigue or a sense of being misunderstood. These reflect the limitations of the current personalized logic of AI recommendation. Furthermore, the perception that recommendation systems are more driven by commercial interests than by user relevance further erodes trust and intensifies skepticism. These findings lead to a more critical establishment of user autonomy.

Theoretically, this thesis advances platform studies and digital sociology by illustrating how users interpret algorithmic systems through emotionally and ethically laden discourse. It highlights that the interaction between users and algorithms is not merely a unidirectional process of information transmission and reception, but a complex, contested, and interdependent dynamic relationship shaped by cultural narratives, platform design, and underlying power imbalances. Drawing on ANT theory, this thesis proposes a perspective that views AI recommendation systems as interwoven social-technical agents within the broader negotiations of identity, trust, and community in digital life. Additionally, it offers valuable advice into designing intelligent recommendation systems that foster transparency and uphold social responsibility.

References

- Akrich, M. (1992). The De-Description of Technical Objects. In W. E. Bijker & J. Law (Eds.), *Shaping technology/Building society: Studies in sociotechnical change* (pp. 205–224). MIT Press.
- Akrich, M. & Latour, B. (1992). A Summary of a Convenient Vocabulary for the Semiotics of Human and Nonhuman Assemblies. In W. E. Bijker & J. Law (Eds.), *Shaping technology/Building society: Studies in sociotechnical change* (pp. 259–264). MIT Press.
- Alboqami, H. (2023). Trust me, I'm an influencer! – Causal recipes for customer trust in artificial intelligence influencers in the retail industry. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 72, Article 103242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2022.103242>
- Baym, N. K. (2010). *Personal Connections in the Digital Age*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Baudier, P., de Boissieu, E., & Duchemin, M.-H. (2023). Source credibility and emotions generated by robot and human influencers: The perception of luxury brand representatives. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 187, Article 122255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122255>
- Beer, D. (2009). Power through the algorithm? Participatory web cultures and the technological unconscious. *New Media & Society*, 11(6), 985-1002. <https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1177/1461444809336551> (Original work published 2009)
- Belk, R. W., Ger, G., & Askegaard, S. (2003). The fire of desire: A multi-sited inquiry into consumer passion. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 30(2), 311–325.
- Berry, D. & Moss, G. (2008). *Libre culture: meditations on free culture*. University of Sussex. Book. <https://hdl.handle.net/10779/uos.23398100.v1>
- Bock, A., Macgilchrist, F., Rabenstein, K., & Wagener-Böck, N. (2024). Hoping for community in a technologically decelerated world: A critical utopian approach. *Futures*, 163, Article 103434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2024.103434>
- Bojic, L. (2024). AI alignment: Assessing the global impact of recommender systems. *Futures*, 160, Article 103383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2024.103383>
- Bontridder, N., & Pouillet, Y. (2021). The role of artificial intelligence in disinformation. *Data & Policy*, 3, e32. doi:10.1017/dap.2021.20

- Bryman, A. (2012). *Social research methods* (4th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Cammaerts, B. (2008). Critiques on the participatory potentials of Web 2.0. *Communication, Culture & Critique*, 1(3), 358–377.
<https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1111/j.1753-9137.2008.00028.x>
- Castells, M. (2000). *The Rise of the Network Society*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Castells, M. (2009). *Communication power*. Oxford University Press.
- Chang, W., & Park, J. (2024). A comparative study on the effect of ChatGPT recommendation and AI recommender systems on the formation of a consideration set. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 78, 103743.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2024.103743>
- Christakis, N. A., & J. H. Fowler. (2009). *Connected: How Your Friends' Friends' Friends Affect Everything You Feel, Think, and Do*. New York: Nack Bay Books.
- Cunliffe, A.L. (2008) 'Discourse analysis', in R. Thorpe and R. Holt (eds), *The SAGE Dictionary of Qualitative Management Research*. London: Sage, pp. 81–2
- Dodeja, L., Tambwekar, P., Hedlund-Botti, E., & Gombolay, M. (2023). Towards the design of user-centric strategy recommendation systems for collaborative Human–AI tasks. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 184, Article 103216.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhcs.2023.103216>
- Easterby-Smith, M., Jaspersen, L. J., Thorpe, R., & Valizade, D. (2021). *Management and business research* (7th ed.). SAGE Publications
- Facebook. (n.d.). *Terms of service*. Facebook. <https://www.facebook.com/terms>
- Fairclough, N. (1992). *Discourse and Social Change*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Feenberg, A. (2009). Critical Theory of Communication Technology: Introduction to the Special Section. *The Information Society*, 25(2), 77–83.
<https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1080/01972240802701536>
- Goffman, E. (1990). *The presentation of self in everyday life*. Penguin.
- Gillespie, T. (2010). The politics of 'platforms'. *New Media & Society*, 12(3), 347-364.
<https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1177/1461444809342738>

- Granovetter, M. (1985). Economic Action and Social Structure: The Problem of Embeddedness. *American Journal of Sociology*, 91(3), 481–510.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/2780199>
- Harris, G., & Abedin, B. (2016). Participating or not participating? A sociomaterial perspective of the embeddedness of online communities in everyday life. *Proceedings of the Australasian Conference on Information Systems (ACIS)*, 2016.
<https://arxiv.org/abs/1605.04714>
- Hsieh, H. F., & Shannon, S. E. (2005). Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative Health Research*, 15(9), 1277–1288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732305276687>
- Kim, Y., Hsu, S.-H., & Gil de Zúñiga, H. (2013). Influence of social media use on discussion network heterogeneity and civic engagement: The moderating role of personality traits. *Journal of Communication*, 63(3), 498–516. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12034>
- Kozinets, R. V. (2002). The Field behind the Screen: Using Netnography for Marketing Research in Online Communities. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 39(1), 61–72.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/1558584>
- Kozinets, R.V., Patterson, A., & Ashman, R. (2017). Networks of Desire: How Technology Increases Our Passion to Consume. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 43(5), 659–682.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/26570335>
- Kozinets, R. V. (2020). *Netnography: The essential guide to qualitative social media research*. SAGE Publications.
- Kumar, R., Shankar, A., Katiyar, G., Mehrotra, A., & Alzeiby, E. A. (2024). Consumer engagement in chatbots and voicebots: A multiple-experiment approach in the online retailing context. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 78, Article 103728.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2024.103728>
- Lash, S. (2006). Dialectic of information? A response to Taylor. *Information, Communication & Society*, 9(5), 572–581. <https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1080/13691180600965542>
- Lash, S. (2007). Power after Hegemony: Cultural Studies in Mutation? *Theory, Culture & Society*, 24(3), 55-78. <https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1177/0263276407075956> (Original work published 2007)

Latour, B. (1992). Where are the missing masses? The sociology of a few mundane artifacts. In W. E. Bijker & J. Law (Eds.), *Shaping technology/Building society: Studies in sociotechnical change* (pp. 225–258). MIT Press.

Latour, B. (2005). *Reassembling the Social: an Introduction to Actor-Network-Theory*. E-book, Oxford: Oxford University Press,
<https://hdl-handle-net.ezp.sub.su.se/2027/heb32135.0001.001>.

Lindbäck, J. (2023). *Novel algorithms for optimal transport via splitting methods* (Licentiate thesis, KTH Royal Institute of Technology). KTH DiVA Portal.
<https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2:1814249>

Lu, Y., & Zhang, J. (2025). Balancing identity diversity and product contexts: Understanding consumer trust in AI-enhanced chatbot services. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 84, Article 104205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2024.104205>

Manjre, B., Chandankhede, P., Jadhav, P. V., Mahajan, R. A., Gawande, R. M., & Meshram, V. H. (2024). Exploring the synergy between artificial intelligence and computational mathematics in scientific computing. *Panamerican Mathematical Journal*, 34(2).

Markovitch, D. G., Stough, R. A., & Huang, D. (2024). Consumer reactions to chatbot versus human service: An investigation in the role of outcome valence and perceived empathy. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 79, Article 103847.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2024.103847>

Muñiz, A. M., Jr., & O'Guinn, T. C. (2001). Brand community. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 27(4), 412–432. <https://doi.org/10.1086/319618>

Newman, M. E. J. (2003). *The structure and function of complex networks*. *SIAM Review*, 45(2), 167–256.

Papacharissi, Z. (2009). The virtual geographies of social networks: a comparative analysis of Facebook, LinkedIn and ASmallWorld. *New Media & Society*, 11(1-2), 199-220.
<https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1177/1461444808099577> (Original work published 2009)

Pariser, E. (2011). *The Filter Bubble: What the Internet Is Hiding from You*. New York: Viking.

Poritz, J. A. (2007). Who Searches the Searchers? Community Privacy in the Age of Monolithic Search Engines. *The Information Society*, 23(5), 383–389.
<https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1080/01972240701572921>

Rohden, S. F., & Zeferino, D. G. (2022). Recommendation agents: An analysis of consumers' risk perceptions toward artificial intelligence. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 23(4), 975–999. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-022-09626-9>

Sherry, J. F., Jr. (1991). Postmodern alternatives: The interpretive turn in consumer research. In H. H. Kassarian & T. Robertson (Eds.), *Handbook of consumer research* (pp. 548–591). Prentice Hall

Schmidt, E., & Cohen, J. (2010). The digital disruption. *Foreign Affairs*, 89(6), 75-85. Retrieved March 26, 2025, from <https://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=aph&AN=54624936&site=ehost-live&scope=site>

Statista. (2023). *Number of social media users worldwide from 2017 to 2023 (in billions)*. Statista. Retrieved March 22, 2025, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/278414/number-of-worldwide-social-network-users/>

Thorat, P. B., Goudar, R. M., & Barve, S. (2015). Survey on collaborative filtering, content-based filtering and hybrid recommendation system. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 110(4), 31–36.

u/ChurrosComics, 2024. *Recommendation System Trap* [web comics]. Reddit.

[Recommendation System](#)

[Trap](https://www.reddit.com/r/comics/comments/1doxvcz/recommendation_system_trap_oc/)https://www.reddit.com/r/comics/comments/1doxvcz/recommendation_system_trap_oc/ [OC]: r/comics

van Dijck, J. (2009). Users like you? Theorizing agency in user-generated content. *Media, Culture & Society*, 31(1), 41-58. <https://doi-org.ezp.sub.su.se/10.1177/0163443708098245> (Original work published 2009)

van Dijck, J. (2013). *The culture of connectivity: A critical history of social media* (online ed.). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199970773.001.0001>

van Maanen, J. (1988). *Tales of the field: On writing ethnography*. University of Chicago Press.

Wang, Y., Liu, W., & Yao, M. (2024). Which recommendation system do you trust the most? Exploring the impact of perceived anthropomorphism on recommendation system trust, choice confidence, and information disclosure. *New Media & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448231223517>

Xiao, B., & Benbasat, I. (2007). E-Commerce Product Recommendation Agents: Use, Characteristics, and Impact. *MIS Quarterly*, 31(1), 137–209.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/25148784>

Zednik, C. (2021). Solving the black box problem: A normative framework for explainable artificial intelligence. *Philosophy & Technology*, 34(2), 265–288.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13347-019-00382-7>